

Research Report on
**Prevalence of Cardiovascular risk factors among the adult population in a rural
municipality of Lumbini Province, Nepal**

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Summary

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally and Nepal. Most CVDs can be prevented by addressing behavioral risk factors such as tobacco use, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, and harmful use of alcohol using population-wide strategies. Despite the significant burden, little efforts have been made at the community level to combat CVDs. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the prevalence of CVDs risk factors among community residents in a Rajpur rural municipality of Lumbini Province, Nepal.

A cross-sectional study design employing a quantitative research method was conducted between September-October 2021. The study was community-based and was carried out among 325 community residents in Rajpur rural municipality of Dang district located in Lumbini Province, Nepal. A modified WHO-NCD STEP survey questionnaire was used to collect information about socio-demographics and CVDs risk factors from the participants. Data collected from KoBo Collect mobile application was extracted via ODK aggregate into CSV spreadsheets which were then exported to IBM SPSS version 20 for analysis. Inter-group comparison among individuals was made using Chi-square for categorical variables and Student's t-test for quantitative variables. The test was two-tailed, and $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

The mean age of the respondents was 35.8 ± 13.8 (SD) years. A considerable proportion of the study population were current smokers (44% male and 9.3% female) and current alcohol users (46% male and 9.8% female). Gender was significantly associated with both current tobacco use and current alcohol use. The mean intake of fruit intake was less than three days per week which suggests that fruit is not a part of the diet in the population. Among the participants, 36.3% have never measured their blood pressure, while only 4% of the participants have ever measured their blood sugar level and blood cholesterol. 24% of the participants were overweight/obese, while 18.5% were underweight. 18.2% of the participants (26% male and 14.6% female) had higher raised blood pressure with a significant difference across gender.

This study concludes that the prevalence of cardiovascular disease risk factors such as tobacco use, alcohol use, and inadequate fruit and vegetable intake was high among the rural population, demanding behavior change communication interventions focusing on improving healthy behaviors. Community-based interventions are required to encourage people to improve the screening behavior of metabolic risk factors, namely hypertension, diabetes, and blood cholesterol.

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

Background

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally and Nepal. An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2016, representing 31% of global deaths. Over three-quarters of CVDs death took place in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) (1). The rapidly increasing CVDs death toll is predicted to rise to 23 million by 2030 (2). Besides, Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including CVDs, are exerting an enormous burden on the lives of poor and marginalized people, reducing labor productivity and increasing out pocket expenditure, and ultimately creating more pressure on the poor health care system, debilitating the national economy (2,3). The CVDs, namely Ischemic heart disease and stroke, are the first and fourth leading cause of premature deaths and the first and fifth leading cause of death and disability, respectively, in Nepal (4). The CVDs were the second most common (40%) NCDs among indoor patients in the hospitals of Nepal (5).

Most CVDs can be prevented by addressing behavioral risk factors such as tobacco use, unhealthy diet and obesity, physical inactivity, and harmful use of alcohol using population-wide strategies. People with CVDs or who are at risk (due to the presence of one or more factors such as hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia or already established disease) need early detection and management using counseling and medicine, as appropriate (1). Among the top-ten risk factors contributing to deaths and disability, eight of them contribute to CVDs in Nepal (4). People who suffer from NCDs including CVDs in LMICs like Nepal have less access to quality, affordable and equitable health care services which respond to their needs. As a result, many people in LMICs are detected late in the course of the disease and die younger from CVDs, often in their most productive years (1). The CVD risk factors like smoking increase the likelihood of being hypertensive by two folds, and the odds of having hypertension increase by 1.6 times with the use of alcohol (6). Hypertension is again an important risk factor for CVDs. Among South Asian countries, Nepal reported the second-highest proportion of hypertensive people (27.3%) after Afghanistan (29%) (7).

Primary health care serves as the cornerstone for building a strong health care system that ensures positive health outcomes and equity (8). Primary care has great potential to improve population health outcomes through early intervention in the disease process and coordinated provision of

care (9). Strong primary health care systems are associated with reduced morbidity, increased patient longevity, and increased equity in health outcomes in several countries. Most research about primary health care performance has been done in high-income settings and has been based on metrics that were not available in LMICs like ours (10, 11).

Effective community-based preventive and control strategies will be a useful strategy to avoid the health and economic consequences of CVDs. Our study aimed to determine the prevalence of CVDs among community residents in a rural municipality and assess the health facility's capacity in response to CVDs. The study findings are expected to serve as a baseline to develop a community-based intervention for preventing and managing CVDs in the near future in the study area.

Rationale of the study

Despite the national burden, little efforts have been made at the community level to combat CVDs. At the sub-national (province and local government) level, there is even scarce information about the magnitude of risk factors.

Goal 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has spelled out the need to reduce premature deaths due to NCDs with a focus on prevention and treatment and decreasing tobacco and alcohol use in the population. As Nepal has currently experienced federal governance, the role of local-level government is influential in overseeing the health sector, including the prevention of NCDs. In this regard, local governments can play an important role by designing interventions to reduce CVDs risk factors. However, this will require the generation of evidence, prioritizing the prevention of CVDs as a social agenda, and building partnership across communities and different sectors for effective response.

Karma Health is a non-profit organization working in Rajpur rural municipality of Dang district in Province 5 of Nepal since October 2017. Karma Health has signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Rajpur rural municipality to improve health status through human resource support and community-based services. This research has set the baseline for developing community-based interventions to prevent and manage risk factors. The design and implementation of the intervention package following the study will be conducted jointly by Karma Health and the Rajpur rural municipality.

Research objective

General Objective

To identify the prevalence of CVDs risk factors and assess health facility capacity for its prevention and management in Rajpur rural municipality of Province 5

Specific Objectives

- To assess the prevalence of behavioral risk factors (tobacco use, alcohol use, physical activity, dietary habit)
- To identify the prevalence of biological risk factors (blood pressure, obesity status, waist circumference)

CHAPTER II: METHODOLOGY

Study design and study area

A cross-sectional study design employing a quantitative research method was conducted between September-October 2021. The study was community-based and carried out in the Rajpur rural Dang district municipality located in Lumbini Province, Nepal. Rajpur rural municipality has a population of 29,410 with 19719 population of 15 and above years of age. The rural municipality is administratively divided into seven wards and is inhabited by indigenous Janajatis (43.8%), Madheshi (20.6%), Brahmin/Chhetri (17.5%), Dalit (15.2%), and others (4.8%). The study population for this study was an adult population of 15+ years of age.

Figure 1: Map of Rajapur rural municipality

Sampling

Stratified proportionate sampling was done for sampling where strata were the administrative division of the municipality (ward). We calculated the sample size using one sample situation of estimating population proportion with specified absolute precision formula. (10)

$$n = z^2 pq / d^2$$

Where, n= sample size

z= reliability level (1.96)

p= estimated proportion in population= 0.25 (prevalence of hypertension taken from STEPS Survey 2019).

$$q = 1 - p = 1 - 0.25 = 0.75$$

d=maximum tolerable error (0.05)

Taking 10% as non-response, the final sample size calculated was 318. However, since the data was collected parallelly by field enumerators, the total data collected was 325.

The sampling strategy for data collection is described in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Sampling strategy

Data collection

Data enumerators were community health workers recruited by the Rajpur rural municipality in 2017. These community health workers are different from the Female Community Health Volunteers (FCHVs) and have passed higher secondary education. All data enumerators were trained for two days in interviewing, filling questionnaires, and measuring the blood pressure and anthropometric measurements. Field supervisors from Karma Health supervised data enumerators.

Data was collected through face-to-face interviews and taking anthropometric and clinical measurements (Table 1). Data will be recorded in Open Data Kit (KoBocollect) mobile application. A modified WHO-NCD STEP questionnaire was used to collect information about socio-demographics and CVDs risk factors. Demographic information included age, sex, ethnicity, marital status, education, and primary occupation.

The health behaviors include tobacco use, alcohol consumption, fruit and vegetable consumption, and physical activity. Tobacco use questions were asked to identify current users, daily users, and past users. Alcohol consumptions question was asked to determine the current users. Dietary consumption for the last seven days was used to estimate fruit and vegetable consumption. Seven-day history of physical activity was recorded.

Weight and height were measured using the digital weighing machines and the measuring tape, respectively, from which Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated. The trained data collector measured blood pressure using a digital blood pressure monitor. Before taking the measurements, participants were requested to sit quietly and rest for 10 minutes with their legs uncrossed.

Table 1: Tools and techniques of data collection

Techniques	Tools	Participants	Data generated
Structured interview	Modified WHO-NCD STEP Questionnaire	Sample Population	Socio-demographics, risk factors
Anthropometric measurement	Digital weighing machine, measuring tape	Sample Population	BMI, waist circumference
Blood pressure	Digital blood pressure monitor	Sample Population	Blood pressure

Data analysis

Data collected from KoBo Collect mobile application was extracted via ODK aggregate into csv spreadsheets which was then exported to IBM SPSS version 20 for analysis.

The prevalence rate was given in percentage. Inter-group comparison among individuals was done by using Chi-square for categorical variables and Student's t-test for quantitative variables. The entire test was two-tailed, and $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Ethics

Ethical approval was taken from the Ethical Review Board of the Nepal Health Research Council, Kathmandu. Written informed consent was taken from the study participants. The study participants were informed about the confidentiality of information collected and their right to withdraw from the study at any time.

CHAPTER III: RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

The mean age of the respondents was 35.8 ± 13.8 (SD) years, and the majority (60%) were in the age group of 20-39 years. Nearly seventy percent of the participants were female. Most of the participants were from Brahmin/Chhetri (26.2%) ethnic groups, followed by Janajati (25.8%) ethnic groups. More than 90% were ever married, and 6.5% had completed higher education. Around 44% of the participants were engaged in agriculture, while one-fourth were involved in household work during the past 12 months. (Table 2)

Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n=325)

Characteristics	Number (Percentage)
Age (Mean \pm SD), years	35.8 (\pm 13.8)
<20	19 (5.8)
20-39	195 (60.0)
40-59	80 (24.6)
60 and above	31 (9.5)
Sex	
Male	100 (30.8)
Female	225 (69.2)
Ethnicity	
Brahmin/Chhetri	85 (26.2)
Janajati	84 (25.8)
Dalit	58 (17.8)
Tharu	56 (17.2)
Madhesi	42 (12.9)
Education	
Illiterate	71 (21.8)
Informal/below primary level	108 (33.2)
Primary level	67 (20.6)
Secondary level	58 (17.8)
Higher education (+2 and above)	21 (6.5)
Marital status	
Ever married	293 (90.2)
Unmarried	32 (9.8)
Occupation	

Agriculture	142 (43.7)
Household work	79 (24.3)
Daily wage worker	31 (9.5)
Unemployed	26 (8.0)
Government/private job	21 (6.5)
Business	13 (4.0)
Foreign employment	13 (4.0)

Behavioral risk factors for CVDs

Tobacco use and alcohol consumption

Table 3 presents the participants' data on alcohol consumption and tobacco use. Among the study participants, 37.8% (70% male and 23.6% female) had ever consumed alcohol, while one-fifth of them were current alcohol drinkers. There was a significant difference in ever use and current use of alcohol across gender ($p < 0.001$). Among the participants, 37.8% (69% male and 24% female) had ever smoked any form of tobacco in their lifetime. There was a significant difference in smoking prevalence and current smoking across gender ($p < 0.001$). The overall prevalence of current smoking was 20.0% (44% male and 9.3% female)..

Table 3: Alcohol consumption and tobacco among study participants (n=325)

Indicators	Overall prevalence n (%)	Male (n=100) n (%)	Female (n=225) n (%)	P-value
Ever consumed alcohol	123 (37.8)	70 (70.0)	53 (23.6)	<0.001
Current alcohol drinkers	68 (20.9)	46 (46.0)	22 (9.8)	<0.001
Ever used any forms of tobacco smoking	123 (37.8)	69 (69.0)	54 (24.0)	<0.001
Current smoker	65 (20.0)	44 (44.0)	21 (9.3)	<0.001

Tobacco and alcohol use by ethnicity

The proportion of current tobacco use was highest in Janajati ethnic group (27.4%) and least in Brahmin/Chhetri (16.5%). Similarly, the proportion of current alcohol use was higher in Tharu (32.1%) and least in Brahmin/Chhetri ethnic group (10.6%). Ethnicity was not significantly associated with current tobacco use ($p=0.408$) but was significantly associated with alcohol use ($p=0.035$).

Figure 2: Current Tobacco and alcohol use across ethnicity

Consumption of fruits and vegetables

In this study, 62.5% (65% male and 61.3% female) of the participants consumed fruits in the last 7 days preceding the survey and 92.6% (89% male and 94.2% female) consumed green vegetables within that period. The mean days of fruit and vegetable intake was 2.8 (± 1.7) days/week and 5.6 (± 1.5) days/week, respectively. There was no significant difference in mean days of fruit and vegetable per week across gender (Table 4).

Table 4: Consumption of fruits and vegetables (n=325)

Indicators	Overall prevalence n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	p-value
Consumed fruits in last 7 days	203 (62.5)	65 (65.0)	138 (61.3)	0.52
Number of days of fruit consumption per week (Mean \pm SD)	2.8 (± 1.7)	2.8 (1.7)	2.8 (1.8)	0.94 [#]
Consumed green vegetables in last 7 days	301 (92.6)	89 (89.0)	216 (96.0)	0.02
Number of days consuming green vegetables per week (Mean \pm SD)	5.5 (± 1.6)	5.4 (± 1.9)	5.6 (± 1.5)	0.35 [#]

[#] Independent samples t-test

Consumption of fruit and vegetable intake across ethnicity

The participants were asked to report the consumption of fruits and vegetable intake within last 7 days. Interestingly, there was significant difference in fruit and vegetables intake across ethnicity ($p < 0.001$). The proportion of fruit intake was highest in Janajati (71.4%) and least in Madhesi ethnic group (28.6%). Similarly, the proportion of vegetable intake was highest in Dalit (100%)

and least in Tharu (78.6%).

Figure 3: Fruit and vegetable intake in last week

Physical activity among the study participants

The proportion of study participants engaged in a vigorous and moderate level of physical intensity was 82.5% and 93.8%, respectively. Similarly, the mean number of days/week for a vigorous and moderate level of physical activity were 4.6 (± 3.2) and 5.1 (± 2.2), respectively. There was a significant difference in mean days of involvement in vigorous ($p=0.04$) and moderate ($p=0.002$) levels of physical activity per week across gender.

Table 5: Physical activity among the study participants (n=325)

Indicators	Overall prevalence n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	p-value
Vigorous level of physical activity for at least 10 mins	268 (82.5)	86 (86.0)	182 (80.9)	0.26
Number of days of involvement in vigorous level of activity per week (Mean \pm SD)	4.6 (± 3.2)	5.2 (± 4.7)	4.4 (± 2.1)	0.04 [#]
Moderate level of physical activity for at least 10 mins	305 (93.8)	93 (93.0)	212 (94.2)	0.67
Number of days of involvement in moderate level of activity per week (Mean \pm SD)	5.1 (± 2.2)	4.5 (± 2.3)	5.4 (± 2.2)	0.002 [#]

[#] Independent samples t-test

Physical activity across ethnicity

There was no significant difference in involvement in vigorous physical activity across ethnicity ($p=0.209$). Janajati participants (89.3%) were involved more in vigorous physical activity while Brahmin/Chhetri were involved less in physical activity (75.3%). Ethnicity was however significantly associated with the involvement in moderate physical activity ($p=0.005$). The proportion of involvement in moderate physical activity ranged from 85.9% in Brahmin/Chhetri to 100% in Madhesi ethnic group. Interestingly, there was significant difference in mean days of involvement in vigorous ($p=0.001$) and moderate physical activity ($p<0.001$) across ethnicity.

Figure 4; Involvement in physical activity across ethnicity

Screening history for metabolic risk factors

Table 6 shows the screening history for blood pressure, diabetes, and cholesterol among the study participants. Overall, 63.7%, 4%, and 4.3% of the participants had ever screened for blood pressure, sugar level, and cholesterol level respectively. Likewise, 10.2%, 2.4% and 0.3% of the participants were previously diagnosed as hypertensive, diabetic, and dyslipidemia respectively. Among participants who had history of raised BP and diabetes, 54.5% and 87.5% of them were currently taking medication, respectively.

Table 6: Screening for BP, Diabetes, and Cholesterol level

Indicators	Overall prevalence n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	P-value
Ever screened for BP (n=325)	207 (63.7)	57 (57.0)	150 (66.7)	0.09
Screened BP by health worker in last 6 months (n=325)	136 (41.8)	38 (38.0)	98 (43.6)	0.34
Previously diagnosed as having hypertension (n=325)	33 (10.2)	11 (11.0)	22 (9.8)	0.73
Taking antihypertensive medicine (n=33)	18 (54.6)	9 (81.8)	9 (40.9)	
Ever screened sugar level/diabetes by health worker (n=325)	13 (4.0)	7 (7.0)	6 (2.7)	0.06
Previously diagnosed as having diabetes (n=325)	8 (2.4)	4 (4.0)	4 (1.8)	0.25
Taking diabetes medication (n=8)	7 (87.5)	4 (100.0)	3 (75.0)	
Screened cholesterol level by health worker (n=325)	14 (4.3)	4 (4.0)	10 (4.4)	1.0
Previously diagnosed as having cholesterol (n=325)	1 (0.3)	1 (1.0)	0	
Taking cholesterol medication	0	0	0	

Figure 5: Screening and medication history of BP, DM, and Cholesterol

Obesity and hypertension status among the study participants

The mean body mass index of the participants was $22.4 \pm 4.6 \text{ kg/m}^2$ with significant difference in mean BMI across gender. The overall prevalence of overweight/obesity was 24.0% across all

participants with higher proportion in male (32%) than female (20.4%). Similarly, female (58/223, 26%) had higher waist circumference compared to male participants (8/99, 8.1%).

Likewise, 18.2% of the participants had raised blood pressure with significantly higher proportion in male (26%) than female (14.6%). The average systolic and diastolic blood pressure across all participants was 122.0 (\pm 32.9) mm of Hg and 74.0 (\pm 11.3) mm of Hg respectively.

Table 7: Obesity and hypertension status among the study participants

BMI	Overall prevalence n (%)	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	P-value
BMI (Mean \pm SD)	22.4 (\pm 4.6)	23.5 (\pm 4.8)	21.9 (\pm 4.4)	0.004 [#]
BMI category				
Underweight	60 (18.5)	12 (12.0)	48 (21.3)	0.059
Normal	187 (57.5)	56 (56.0)	131 (58.2)	
Overweight	56 (17.2)	22 (22.0)	34 (15.1)	
Obesity	22 (6.8)	10 (10.0)	12 (5.3)	
Waist circumference (Mean\pmSD)	83.4 (10.7)	85.8 (10.8)	82.4(10.5)	
Adults with high waist circumference than cut-off (n=322)	66 (20.5)	8 (8.0)	58 (26.0)	
Blood pressure				
Average systolic blood pressure (Mean \pm SD)	122.0 (\pm 32.9)	127.9 (\pm 18.0)	119.4 (\pm 37.4)	0.03 [#]
Average diastolic blood pressure (Mean \pm SD)	74.0 (\pm 11.3)	75.9 (\pm 13.8)	73.5 (\pm 10.0)	0.07 [#]
Blood pressure status				
Raised BP	59 (18.2)	26 (26.0)	33 (14.6)	0.01
Normal BP	266 (81.8)	74 (74.0)	192 (85.3)	

[#] Independent samples t-test

Body mass index category across ethnicity

There was significant difference in BMI across ethnicity ($p=0.001$). The proportion of underweight was highest in Madhesi (45.2%) and lowest in Dalit (6.9%) ethnic group. Similarly, the proportion of overweight and obesity was highest in Dalit (36.2%) and lowest in Madhesi (7.2%) ethnic group.

Figure 6; Body mass index category across ethnicity

Raised blood pressure across ethnicity

Ethnicity was significantly associated with the prevalence of raised blood pressure ($p < 0.001$). The proportion of participants with raised blood pressure was highest in Dalit (37.9%) and lowest in Madhesi ethnic group (7.1%).

Figure 7: Raised BP across ethnicity

CHAPTER IV: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

This study identified the prevalence of behavioral and metabolic risk factors of CVDs in a rural municipality in the Dang district.

Tobacco and alcohol use

- A considerable proportion of the study population were current smokers (44% male and 9.3% female) and current alcohol users (46% male and 9.8% female).
- Gender was significantly associated with both current tobacco use and current alcohol use. The proportion of current tobacco and alcohol use was five times more in males than females.
- However, ethnicity was significantly associated only with current alcohol use, with a higher proportion of current alcohol users in the Tharu population.

Fruit and vegetable intake

- Two out of three participants consumed fruits in the last seven days, while nine out of ten consumed vegetables in the same period.
- The mean intake of fruit intake was less than three days per week which suggests that fruit is not a part of the diet in the population.
- Although there were no gender differences in fruit and vegetable intake consumption, ethnicity was significantly associated with both fruit and vegetable intake.
- Consumption of fruit was lowest in Madheshi ethnic group, while vegetable consumption was lowest in the Tharu population.

Physical activity

- Eight out of ten participants were involved in vigorous. In comparison, nine out of ten participants were involved in a moderate level of physical activity, which suggests that study participants were physically active.
- There was a significant difference in mean days of involvement in both moderate and vigorous levels of physical activity in the past week across gender.
- Ethnicity was significantly associated with the involvement in a moderate level of physical activity.

Screening behavior of metabolic risk factors

- 36.3% of the participants have never measured their blood pressure, while nearly three out of five participants have not measured it in the last six months.
- Only 4% of the participants have ever measured their blood sugar level and blood cholesterol.
- One out of ten participants reported having a history of hypertension, among which 54.6% were on anti-hypertensive medication.
- Eight out of 325 participants (2.4%) reported being diabetic, among which seven were taking medication for diabetic control.
- Only one participant mentioned a history of a lipid disorder.

Obesity and hypertension status

- 24% of the participants (32% male and 20.4% female) were overweight/obese while 18.5% of the participants (12% male and 21.3% female) were underweight.
- 20.5% of the participants (8% male and 26% female) had a higher waist circumference
- 18.2% of the participants (26% male and 14.6% female) had higher raised blood pressure with a significant difference across gender.
- Ethnicity was significantly associated with BMI and raised blood pressure status.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion stated above, the study team would like to make the following recommendations.

1. The prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors such as tobacco use, alcohol use, and inadequate fruit and vegetable intake was high among the rural population, demanding behavior change communication interventions focusing on improving healthy behaviors.
2. Community-based interventions are required to encourage people to improve the screening behavior of metabolic risk factors, namely hypertension, diabetes, and blood cholesterol. Such interventions should also focus on treatment and lifestyle change.
3. The double burden of malnutrition was evident in the study population, which demands health interventions to improve the population's nutritional status with a particular focus on the female population.
4. Gender and ethnicity need to be an important consideration during the programming to prevent NCD risk factors in the community.

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Appendix

Informed consent form (Nepali)

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tkfO{sf] ;xefuLtsf] ck]lff ub{5' . d tkfO{nfO{ ;fdfGo, ;fdflhs tyf cfly{s cj:yf, , नसर्ने रोग ;'lt{hGo kbfy{
tyf dfbs kbfy{sf] k|of]u ;DaGwL s]xL s'/fx? ;f]Wg rfxG5' . o;sf] nflu dnfO{ !% b]lv @) ldg]6 nfUg ;S5
. of] hfgsf/L tkfO{sf] ;d'bfosf] :jf:Yo ;jif ;'wf/sf] nflu k|of]u ul/g] 5 . tkfO{sf] lrgf/L tyf k|lts|ofnfO{
uf]Ko /flvg]5 .

o; cWoogdf tkfO{sf] ;xeflutf :j]IR5s x'g]5 . t;y{ obL cGt/jftf{sf] ;dodf tkfO{nfO{ s'g} klG a]nf s'g} klG
k|Zgsf] pQ/ lbg grfxg] jf lard} cGt/jftf{ ;dfKt ug]{ OR5f ePdf tkfO{ To;f] ug{ :jtGq x'g'x'G5 . tkfO{n]
lbg'ePsf] hfgsf/Lx? o; cWoogsf nflu dfq k|of]u ul/g]5 / ;Dk"Of{ ;+slnt hfgsf/Lx? uf]Ko /flvg]5 . o;
cGt/jftf{af6 s'g} ^mfObf jf 3f6f 5}g t/ of] cWoogn] tkfO{ / tkfO{h:t} ;d'bfonfO{ x'g;S5 ^mfObf x'g;S5
. tkfO{af6 k|fKt hfgsf/Ln] eljZodf नसर्ने रोगको sfo{s] d th{'df ug{ ;xof]u k'¥ofpg]5 . tkfO{sf] ;xeflutf o;
cWoogsf nflu dxTjk\0f{ 5 . ;f]w]sf] k|Zgsf] hjf^m lbg'eO{ o; cWoognfO{ ;DkGg ug{ ;xof]u ug'x'G5
eGg] ck]lff /fVb5' / ;xof]usf nflu cfef/L x'g]5' . olb tkfO{nfO{ o; ;DaGwL s'g} lh1f;f ePdf lgw{Ss /fVg
;Sg'x'g]5 . s] tkfO{ cGt/jftf{sf nflu tof/ x'g'x'G5 ?

d ;xefuL x'g OR5's 5' cGt/jftf{ ;'? ug{'xf];\ _

d ;xefuL x'g OR5's 5}g wGojfb lbb}F labf lng'xf];\ _

pQ/bftfaf6 M

d o; cWoogsf] af/]df :ki65' / cGt/jftf{sf nfluL tof/ 5' .

b:vtv =====

jf cf}F7f5fk M

g;g]{ /f]u ;DalGw hf]lvd tTjsf] ;j]{lf0fsf nfluL k|ZgfanL

tkfO{sf] hGd ldl eGg'xf];\ .	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; margin: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; margin: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; margin: 2px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 20px; height: 20px; margin: 2px;"></div> </div> <p style="text-align: center;">lbg dlxgf jif{ hGd ldl ofb gePdf C4 df hfg]</p>	C2	
k"/f ePsf] pd]/	jif{	<div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 30px; height: 20px; margin: 0 auto;"></div>	C3
tkfO{n] ;du df cf}krfl/s lzlfssf nfuL slt jif{ latfpg'eof] < -k"}{ k fylds tx nfO{ ;dfj]z gug}{_	jif{	<div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 30px; height: 20px; margin: 0 auto;"></div>	C4
tkfO{n] k"/f ug'[{ ePsf] dflyNnf] txsf] lziff s'g xf]<	cgf}krfl/s lziff	!	C5
	k fylds eGbf sd	@	
	k fylds tx	#	
	dfWolds tx	\$	
	k ljOftf jf pRr lziff	%	
	sn]h jf ljZ] ljBfno k"/f ePsf]	^	
	kf]i6 uf h'P6 jf ;f] eGbf dfly	&	
	pQ/ lbg grfx]sf]	**	
tkfO{sf] hft s'g xf] < -hflto al{us/of sf8{ k of]u ug}{_	blnt	!	C6
	kx'Fr gePsf hghflt	@	
	kx'Fr gePsf u)/ blnt t/fO{ hflt ;d'x	#	
	wfl{ds ?kn] cNk;+Vos	\$	
	t'ngfTds ?kn] kx'Fr ePsf hghflt?	%	
	pkNnf] ;d'x	^	
	pQ/ lbg grfx]sf]]	**	
tkfO{sf] xfn j}jflxs l:ylt s] xf] <	cljflxt	!	C7
	ljflxt	@	
	5'l\$Psf]	#	
	;DaGw ljR5]b	\$	

	ljb'/ jf l'w'jf	%	
	cljflxt t/ ;u} a:g]	^	
	pQ/ lbg grfx]sf]	**	
ljut !@ dlxgf b]lv tkfO{ d'Vo s'g k]zfdf ;+nUg x'g'x'G5<	;/sf/L hflu/	!	C8
	u);;/sf/L hflu/	@	
	cf`g} :jfldTjsf]	#	
	a]tnaL	\$	
	ljBfyL{	%	
	3/fo;L sfd	^	
	cjsf; k fKt	&	
	j]/f]huf/ -sfd ug{ ;Sg]_	*	
	j]/f]huf/ -sfd ug{ g;Sg]_	(
	pQ/ lbg grfx]sf]]	**	
tkfO{sf] 3/df tkfO{ nufot !% jif{ dflysf slt hgf ;b:ox? x'g'x'G5 <	;b:ox?sf] ;^Vof	<input type="text"/>	C9
tkfO{sf] 3/df ! b]lv !% jif{ d'lgsf] ;b:o slt hgf x'g'x'G5 <	;b:ox?sf] ;^Vof	<input type="text"/>	C10
lj:t[t hg;f^IVos laa/Of s] dz			
tkfO{sf] 3/sf] cf]);t cfo slt x'G5<	Ps xKtfd Ps dlxgfd Ps aif{df pQ/ lbg grfx]sf] **	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	C11

r/Of ! Jojxfl/s dfg		
;!t{hGo kbfy{ ;jg ca d tkfOnfO{ ;!t{hGo w'd kfg ;DalGw s]lx k Zgx? ;f]Wg uO/x]sf] 5' .		
k Zgx?	hjkmx?	sf]8
	u5'{ !	T1

tkfO{n} xfn s'g} ;'lt{hGo w'd kfg ;}jg ug'{x'G5< -h:t} la8L, r'/f]6, tdfv', x'Ssf jf cGo :yflgo ?kdf pTkfbg x'g] ;'lt{thGo kbfy{x?_ ;f] sf8{ k of]u ug}{	ul{bgF	@ ,olb ul{b{gF eg] T8 df hfg]		
s] clxn] b}lgs w'd kfg ug'{x'G5<	u5'{	!	T2	
	ul{bgF	@		
klxnf] k6s b}lgs w'd kfg ug{ z'? ubf{ tkfO{sf] pd]/ slt jif{sf] lyof]<	k"/f ePsf] pd]/	<input type="text"/>	T3	
	ofb gePdf	&&& olb ofb ePdf T5a/T5aw df hfg]		
s] tkfO{ ;Demg'x'G5 slt ;do cuf8L z'? ug'{ePsf] lyof]< Ps hjfkm dfq eg'{xf];\	jif{df	<input type="text"/> olb ofb ePdf T5a/T5aw df hfg]	T4a	
	<i>if</i> dlxgdf	<input type="text"/> olb ofb ePdf T5a/T5aw df hfg]	T4b	
	<i>if</i> xKtfd	<input type="text"/>	T4c	
	ofb gePdf	&&&		
lgDg pNn]lvt w'd kfg lbgdf jf xKtfd cf);t slt ;}jg ug'{x'G5< -k To]s k sf/sf] w'd kfg /]s8{ ug}{_ yxf gePdf &&&		b}lgs	xKtf	
	pTkfbg ul/Psf] r'/f]6	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	T5a/ T5a w
	xftn] a]/]sf] r'/f]6	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	T5b/ T5b w
	kfOk - x'Ssf, lrInd cflb	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	T5c/ T5c w

	l;uf/	<table border="1"><tr><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr></table>				<table border="1"><tr><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr></table>				T5d/ T5d w

dlb/fhGo kbfy{ ;]jg

casf k|Zgx? dlb/fhGo kbfy{ ;]jg ;u ;DalGwt 5g\ .

k Zgx?	hjfkmx?		sf]8
tkfO{n} hLjgdf slxNo} dBkfg ug'{ePsf] 5<-h:t} ljo/ ,jfOg,x'l:s ,uf'p3/d} agfPsf] /S;L, hf+8, tf]Daf_ ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug}{	5 5}g	! @ olb 5}g eg] KA1 df hfg]	A1
tkfO{n} !@ dlxgf leqdf s'g} dlb/fhGo kbfy{sf] ;]jg ug'{ePsf] 5 <	5 5}g	! olb 5 eg] A4 df hfg] @	A2
tkfO{n} dlb/fhGo kbfy{ :jf:Yosf sf/Of 5f8\g' ePsf] xf],jf :jf:Yodf k/]sf] gsf/fTds c;/n] jf :jf:YosdL{sf] 'emfjaf6 5f8\g' ePsf] xf]<	xf] xf]Og	! @ olb xf]Og eg] KA1 df hfg]	A3
ljt]sf] !@ dlxgf leqdf slt ;dosf] cGt/df tkfO{n} dlb/fhGo k]o kbfy{ lkgp'ePsf] lyof] < ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug}{	b}lgs %~^ lbg/ xKtf !~\$ lbg/ xKtf !~# lbg/dlxgf dlxgdf Psk6s eGbf sd	! @ # \$ %	A4
tkfO{n} ljt]sf] ! dlxgdf -#) lbg_ s'g} k sf/sf] dBkfg ug'[{ ePsf] 5 <	5 5}g	! @,olb 5}g eg] A13 df hfg]	A5
ljt]sf] ! dlxgdf -#) lbg_ slt k6s tkfO{n} -slDtdf Ps k6s_ dBkfg ug'{eof] <	lbg ;+Vof yxf 5}g	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> &&	A6
ljt]sf] ! dlxgdf -#) lbg_ tkfO{n} dBkfg u/]sf] lbgdf Ps k6s vbfFcf];tdf slt :6fG88{ l8<S; lng'eof] < ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug}{	;+Vof yxf 5}g	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> &&	A7
] ;+Vof	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	A8

l]t]sf] ! dlxgdf -#) lbg_ tkfO{n] Ps k6s vbfF ;a)eGbf a9L lkPsf] lbg slt :6fG88{ l8«S; lkpg'eof] <	yxf 5)g	&&	
l]t]sf] ! dlxgdf -#) lbg_ tkfO{n] ^ jf ^ eGbf w]/} :6fG88l8«+S; Ps k6s vbfF slt lbg lkpg'ePsf] lyof] <	slt lbg ofb gePdf	<input type="text"/> &&	A9

cfxf/

csf]{ k|Zgx? tkfO{n] b]lgs ?kdf vfPsf] kmnkm'n / ;fu;IAhx?sf] af/]df ;f]lw]5 . oxf' d kf]if0ftTj
;+alGw :yflgo kmnkm'n / ;fu;IAhx?sf] s]lx pbfX/Ofx? tkfO{nfO{ b]vfp'5' . k|To]s lrqn] lnOPsf] dfqf
OlGut u5{ . s[kof tkfO{n] of] k|Zgsf] pQ/ ;f]r]/ lbg'xf];\ .

k Zgx?	hjfkmx?	sf]8
tkfO{ xKtfd] slt lbg kmnkm'n vfg'x'G5 < ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug]{	lbg]sf] ;+Vof ofb gePdf	<input type="text"/> && olb z'Go lbg ePdf D3 df hfg]
tL lbgdWo] Pslbgdf slt ;le{ ^a kmnkm'n vfg'x'G5 ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug]{	lnPsf] ;+Vof ofb gePdf	<input type="text"/> &&
tkfO{ xKtfd] slt lbg xl/of] t/sf/L vfg'x'G5 < ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug]{	lbg]sf] ;+Vof ofb gePdf	<input type="text"/> && olb z'Go lbg ePdf D5 df hfg]
lt lbg dWo] Ps lbgdf slt ;le{ ^a vfg'x'G5< ;f] sf8{sf] k of]u ug]{	lnPsf] ;+Vof ofb gePdf	<input type="text"/> &&

r/Of @M zf/LI/s dfkg			
prfO{ / jhg			
k Zgx?	hjfkmx?	sf]8	
k flj lws÷cGtjf{tf{stf{sf} cfO{ l8	<input type="text"/>	M1	
prfO{ / jhg lng] cf}hf/sf] cfO{ l8	prfO{ <input type="text"/> jhg <input type="text"/>	M2a M2b	
prfO{	;]lG6ld6/df -;]= <input type="text"/>	M3	
jhg lf too large for scale 666.6	lsnf]u fddf -s] <input type="text"/>	M4	
(dlxnfsf] nflu) s] tkfO{ ue{jtL x'g'x'G5<	5' ! olb xf] eg] M8 df hfg] 5)g @	M5	
sDd/sf] gfk] ug]{ cf}hf/sf] cfO{ l8	<input type="text"/>	M6	
sDd/sf] rf}8fO -;] dL_	;]lG6ld6/df -l;=Pd= <input type="text"/>	M7	
k flj lws÷cGtjf{tf{stf{sf} cfO{ l8	<input type="text"/>	M8	
/Qmrfk lng] cf}hf/sf] cfO{ l8	<input type="text"/>	M9	
/Qmrfk lng] cf}hf/sf] k sf/	;fgf] ! dWod @ 7'nf] #	M10	
/Qmrfk -gfk !_	l;:6f]lns (mmHg)	<input type="text"/>	M11a
	8fo:6f]lns (mmHg)	<input type="text"/>	M11b
/Qmrfk -gfk @_	l;:6f]lns (mmHg)	<input type="text"/>	M12a
		<input type="text"/>	M12b

	8fo:6f]Ins (mmHg)		
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